

Effect of Intensity Manipulation of Olympic Lift Training on Reaction Time of Elite Athletes

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present study was to determine effect of intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training on the performance of elite athletes. The subjects were 30 male elite athletes of 18 to 25 years of age group from Lakshmbai National Institute of Physical Education. The subjects were randomly selected and were assigned to the one experimental groups (Intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training) and one control group with 15 subjects in each group. The training was given for a period of 6 weeks. The experimental groups were trained thrice a week, while the control group continued with their daily routine work. The performances of reaction time of the subjects were taken by the Nelson foot reaction test. The Pre and Post test were conducted to collect the data. After the collection of data, the t- test was used to identify any significant differences between the groups. The level of significance was 0.05. The finding have shown the significant value of F-ratio's for selected variable in the experimental group i.e. Intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training programs as compared with the control group. The hypothesis was rejected because of significant differences were observed in the reaction time.

Keywords: Intensity Manipulation, Olympic Lift Training, Reaction Time, Elite Athletes

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INTRODUCTION

Today the sports persons are trained scientifically with the latest training methods and sophisticated instruments for higher performance improvement in different sphere of sports. The modern trends in preparation of sportsman are to proceed in a scientific manner and to take the help of allied sciences to achieve the top level of performance. (William, 1980). Sports performance is indeed an aspect of complex human performance, which has several dimensions. Hence, several disciplines of sports sciences are required to work in a coordinated manner to explore the nature and the process of improving performance. In the last few decades several disciplines of sports sciences have established e.g. sports medicine, sports physiology, sports training, sports bio-mechanics, sports psychology, sports pedagogy, sports nutrition and so on. These sports sciences work as one integrated unit to give super sports performance. (Rachna, 2001). Training is not a recent discovery. In ancient times, people systematically trained for military and Olympic endeavors. Today athletes prepare themselves for a goal through training.(Tudor, 1999). In the recent years greater stress has been laid on the quality rather than the quantity of training. The sports scientists and experts of sports want their sportsman to extract maximum achievement from their training procedure without causing too much strain on them. This is

possible only if coaches and teachers of physical education apply the most economical manner for enhancing the performance of athletes.(Asha, 1980). Over the years this form of training has been employed extensively to improve many power oriented movements in a variety of sports. There are many variations on the theme of power training. Some of these training principles include plyometrics, assisted and resisted training and speed and acceleration drills. A popular method used to increase athletic power is Olympic lifting (ie power cleans, push presses, snatches, jump jerks and their variations) conducted in the weight room. This has traditionally been seen as an effective way of producing general explosive ability. However, considering motor skill and neurological aspects of movement, the logic of employing Olympic Lifts in power training becomes unclear. Therefore, the interpretation and application of Olympic lifting to the development of power will be considered (Takano, 1992).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Subjects

The present study had been undertaken to compare the effect of intensity manipulation of olympic lift training on reaction time of elite athletes. Thirty male elite athletes between the age group of 18 to 25 years of age

had been selected for this study. All of the subjects played at Inter university in athletics and none had been trained by means of a six weeks of training programme and not to alter their normal daily exercise routine throughout the duration of the study. Further the subjects was equally divided in two groups i.e. Group A (N=15) for experimental group, Group B (N=15) control group to give six weeks training.

METHODOLOGY

The Nelson Foot Reaction Test

Objective: To measure the speed of reaction with the foot in response to a visual stimulus.

Test Equipment and Materials: Nelson Reaction Timer, table or bench, well space.

Direction: The subject sits on a table (or bench) which is about 1 inch from the wall. With his shoe off, the subject positions his foot so that the ball of the heel resting on the table about 2 inches from the edge. The tester holds the reaction timer next to the wall and the subject foot with the base line opposite the end of the big toe. The subject looks at the timer is dropped, by pressing the stick against the wall the ball of his foot, Twenty trials are given.

Scoring: The reaction time for each trial is the line just above the end of the big toe. When the foot is pressing the stick to the wall. The slowest five trails and the fastest five trials are discarded, and the average of the middle ten trials is recorded.

Six Week of Olympic Lift Training Programme

Subjects were trained thrice a week i.e. on Monday, Wednesday and Friday. The subjects performed Power Clean, Snatch, Push Press, Push jerk and Split jerk. 10-15 repetitions in each of the 3 sets, with 50% weight of 1 repetition maximum and with 3 min recovery period in between each set. After the two weeks 10-12 repetitions in each of the 3 sets, with 60% of 1 R.M. and recovery period was same as it was in first two weeks. Finally for last two weeks the exercises were performed with 70% weight of 1 R.M., 6-8 repetitions in each of the 3 sets with 2 min recovery period in between sets. The detailed weekly Olympic lift training schedule.

RESULTS

The study was conducted to determine the effects of intensity manipulation of olympic lift training on reaction time of elite athletes. The statistical analysis of data collected on thirty (N=30) subjects. The finding have shown the significant value of F- ratio's for selected variables in the experimental group i.e. Intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training programs as compared with the control group. The

hypothesis was rejected because of significant differences were observed in the reaction time. The results pertaining to significant difference, if any, between experimental and control groups were assessed by "t" test and are presented in following tables:

The Table 1. represent the number of students in experiment group to be 15. The means of reaction time of pre-test and post-test scores of experiment group were 0.22 and 0.21 respectively. The calculated 't' value in case of experimental group is 6.259. The calculated t value was more than the table t value at 0.05 level of significance. Cal. T (=6.259) > tab t.05 (14) (= 2.14), Hence it may be concluded that six week intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training programme showed significant improvement in reaction time. Thus the post-test scores of experimental group were significantly higher than the pre-test scores.

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), Standard Error of Mean (SEM) of Reaction Time of Experimental Group

	Pre-test	Post-test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	0.2212	0.2156
95% CI for the mean	0.2094 to 0.2330	0.2045 to 0.2266
Variance	0.0004525	0.0003985
Standard deviation	0.02127	0.01996
Standard error of the mean	0.005492	0.005154
Mean difference		-0.005653
Standard deviation		0.003498
95% CI		-0.007591 to -0.003716
Test statistic t		6.259
Degrees of Freedom (DF)		14
Two-tailed probability		P < 0.0001

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), Standard Error of Mean (SEM) of Reaction Time of Control Group

	Pre-test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	0.1833	0.1859
95% CI for the mean	0.1640 to 0.2026	0.1663 to 0.2056
Variance	0.001215	0.001255
Standard deviation	0.03486	0.03542
Standard error of the mean	0.0090	0.009146
Mean difference		0.002633
Standard deviation		0.005863
95% CI		-0.0006136 to 0.00588
Test statistic t		1.739
Degrees of Freedom (DF)		14
Two-tailed probability		P = 0.1039

The Table 2 shows the number of student in control group to be 15. The mean of reaction time of pre-test and post-test score of control group were 0.183

and 0.185 respectively. The calculated t value in case of control group is 1.739. The calculated t value was less than the table t value at 0.05 level of significance. $Cal t (= 0.414) < tab t.05 (14) (= 2.14)$. Therefore the calculated t value was not significant. It was interpreted that the mean difference of Reaction time in pre-test and post-test were not significant. Thus there was no effect of intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training on reaction time of control group.

The table 3 shows the result was accomplished that intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training had significant impact in increasing the reaction time of the experimental group. Therefore the hypothesis was rejected. Since there was significant effect of intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training on reaction time.

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), Standard Error of Mean (SEM) of Reaction Time of Experimental and Control Group

Group	Number	Mean	S.D.	SEM	't' Value
Experimental (Pre-test)	15	0.2212	0.02127	0.0054	6.259 *
Experimental (Post-test)	15	0.2156	0.01996	0.0051	
Control (Pre-test)	15	0.1833	0.03486	0.009	1.739
Control (Post-test)	15	0.1859	0.03542	0.0091	

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence.
"t".05 (14) = 2.14

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS

Today the sports persons are trained scientifically with the latest training methods and sophisticated

instruments for higher performance improvement in different sphere of sports. The findings pertaining to the study resolved significant improvement in reaction time the six weeks intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training programme for the elite athletes. The experimental groups were effective in improving the reaction time of the subjects. The intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training programme improving the reaction time of the subjects. In reaction time 't' test analysis showed an equal improvement due to the intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training programme which reveals that Olympic lift training is for improving reaction time. The 't' test analysis on reaction time demonstrated significant differences between experimental group. While the control group were not found significantly different on this variable. This indicates that's the regular practice of Olympic lift improve the reaction time which was required for players in elite athletes. However, there have been improvements of reaction time although in varying degrees as a result of the intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training. This finding of present investigation is in line with the finding of Singh Shamsheer (2006). In conclusion, the present study suggests that the intensity manipulation of Olympic lift training of six week training duration leads to a significant effect on the reaction time of elite athletes. So, in case of reaction time, Olympic lift training was found to effective. The world of training methodology has crossed many milestones. In modern time athletes are being trained by highly sophisticated means for better achievements in their concerned sports, and greater stress has been laid on the quality rather than the quantity of training. Six weeks of intensity manipulation of olympiclift training are useful program to improve the reaction time of elite athletes.

Fig. 1: Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), Standard Error of Mean (SEM) of Reaction Time of Experimental and Control Group

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